

Antibody Characterization Report for Cyclin-F

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Recommended protein name: Cyclin-F

Alternative protein name: F-box only protein 1

Gene name: *CCNF*

Uniprot: P41002

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized 3 Cyclin-F commercial antibodies for Western Blot using a standardized experimental protocol [2] based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. We identified many well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. A U2OS *CCNF* custom KO line was generated at Abcam and was used in this study. U2OS was selected based on evidence of appropriate Cyclin-F protein expression determined through DepMap [3, 4].

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	HTB-96	CVCL_0042	U2OS	WT
Abcam	-	-	U2OS	CCNF KO

Table 2: Summary of the Cyclin-F antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab50811*	GR13068-11	AB_869307	monoclonal	2123D1a	mouse	0.100	other
Cell Signaling Technology	81045**	1	AB_1600000	recombinant-mono	D9K2U	rabbit	n/a	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA536049	XC3523222	AB_2553344	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb

Wb=Western Blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All the Cyclin-F antibodies tested are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520).

CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing

Cell lines used are listed in Table 1. U2OS *CCNF* KO clone was generated at Abcam using two guide RNAs to knockout the *CCNF* gene (sequence guide 1: CGGGGAGACTCAAGATGGTC, sequence guide 2: GCAGGGACTTACAGCTCGGA).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamate (Wisent cat. number 609065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201).

Cells were synchronized by double thymidine block followed by an eight-hour release into complete medium to collect cells in the G2 phase, when Cyclin F is at its peak [5, 6]. Thymidine from MilliporeSigma (cat. number T1895) was used at 2mM.

Antibody screening by Western Blot

Western Blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [7]. U2OS WT and *CCNF* KO were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number 78429). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and Western Blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western Blots were performed with precast midi 10% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WXP01020BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer from bio-Rad (cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual Western Blot. Blots were blocked

with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Clarity Western ECL Substrate from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Figure 1: Cyclin-F antibody screening by Western Blot

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Lysates of U2OS WT and *CCNF* KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for Western Blot with the indicated Cyclin-F antibodies. U2OS remained untreated (-) or were synchronized in the G2 phase by a double thymidine block followed by an 8 hours release into complete medium (+). The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. All antibodies were tested at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 87 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

References

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